

AN INVESTIGATION ON SOIL AND PEAT HUMIC ACIDS. PART I. ISOLATION AND PURIFICATION OF THE ACIDS.

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Two humic acids isolated from two Assam tea soils have been compared with two commercial humic acids isolated from peat in regard to the content of C, H, N, OMe, acetyl and furfural and formaldehyde-yielding groups.

The organic matter of soils and of peat has engaged the attention of the scientific investigators ever since the latter part of the 18th century. Although various theories have been proposed, the origin and the constitution of humic acid are still incompletely understood.

Achard (Crell's *Chem. Ann.*, 1786, 2, 391) first used the alkali extraction method for isolation of humic acid from peat. Sprengel (*Kastner's A. Ges. Naturalchre*, 1826, 8, 145) described the preparation and properties of humic acid and its salts for the first time.

Seyler (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1889, 13, 647) studied both artificial and natural humic acids. He distinguished these groups of humus substances on the basis of their solubilities in alkali and alcohol, and concluded that in the natural decomposition of plant residues, lignin complexes take active part in the production of humic acid.

By applying modern physicochemical methods of investigations, Odén (*Koll-Chem. Beihefte*, 1919, 11, 75) tried to give an idea about the origin and chemistry of various humic acids. He isolated humic acid from peat and soil by treating these first with an acid, washing with water and extracting overnight with 4*N*-ammoniacal or sodium hydroxide solution. Sufficient sodium chloride was then added to the alkali solution to make it 2*N*. The dark coloured filtrate, obtained after centrifuging, was concentrated, acidified with hydrochloric acid in presence of sodium chloride, centrifuged and washed. This precipitate was treated with alcohol. The alcohol-insoluble portion was called humic acid and the alcohol-soluble portion hymatomalanic acid. He concluded that humus acid and hymatomalanic acid were definite chemical entities. Page (*Agric Sci.*, 1930, 20, 455) suggested the term humic matter to describe the dark coloured high molecular colloidal organic bodies found in soils and composts. He referred to that part of the humic matter, which is soluble in cold weak alkali and is precipitated by acids, as 'humic' acid and the part, insoluble in cold alkali but soluble in hot alkali solution, as humin. Later on Springer, Karrer.

Maliktin and others reported that acetyl bromide is the reagent which can separate lignin and other plant constituents from humic acids. Thus Karrer (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, **4**, 700) and Groszkopf (*Brennstoff. Chem.*, 1929, **10**, 116, 213) showed that the undecomposed plant constituents which are mixed with humus are easily dissolved by acetyl bromide, while the dark coloured, modified and synthesised complexes remain insoluble. Lignin has also been found to be soluble in this reagent. Springer (*Pflanz, Dung. Bod.*, 1931, **A22**, 135) has demonstrated that the humic acid isolated from soil by means of acetyl bromide contained comparatively large proportion of nitrogen and hence concluded that the soil humus contains both nitrogen-containing and nitrogen-free humic acids. It has been found in this laboratory that the so-called hymatomelanin acid (alcohol-soluble portion of the crude humic acids) both from soil and peat is completely soluble in hot acetyl bromide. All the crude (untreated with alcohol) humic acids, when treated with acetyl bromide in a soxhlet, goes into solution to the extent of 30-35%, while the alcohol-insoluble humic acid is but slightly soluble in the reagent even when treated for a week. Jute lignin, previously isolated in this laboratory, has been subjected to this reagent side by side. Almost the whole of it goes into solution but with much difficulty and in a considerable period of time. Purification of humic acid by this reagent is a very tedious task. However, in view of the fact that all the undecomposed portions of humus are removed by this reagent and that a purer staff is obtained, alcohol-extraction is followed by acetyl bromide extraction in the present investigation.

Up to the end of the 19th century, the origin of the natural humic acids was looked for in the carbohydrate part of the decaying plant materials and wood cellulose was regarded as the precursor of natural humic acid. Fischer and Scharder (*Brennstoff. Chem.*, 1921, **2**, 37 ; 1922, **3**, 65, 341) put forward their lignin theory of the origin of humic acid and of coal, according to which the cellulose is largely destroyed by bacterial decomposition, the lignin fraction being more resistant, remains intact, but during humification it is modified and also possibly polymerised to form humic acid. According to Waksman (*Soil Sci.*, 1932, **34**, 43 ; 1933, **36**, 57) humus formation is largely due to the activities of the micro-organisms which decompose the natural plant and animal residues, like cellulose, hemi-cellulose, pectin etc., but leave the more resistant lignin behind, combined during this decomposition with microbial protein, producing a modified 'lignin-protein complex' which forms the nucleus of the humic acids.

The object of the present investigation is to compare the physical and chemical properties of humic acids obtained from various sources with

a view to finding out whether they are closely related or otherwise and whether they contain any common molecular framework. For this purpose a comparative study of the nature and relative number of the active groups (hydroxyl and carboxyl), and the products of oxidation etc. is necessary.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of Humic Acid from Soil.

Like Odèn, Page, Waksman and other earlier investigators and following specially the method of Waksman and Stevens (*Soil Sci.*, 1939, **30**, 97) the soil was first extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with a mixture of alcohol and benzene (1 : 1) to free it from fats, waxes and resinous matters. After evaporating off the adhering alcohol-benzene, the soil was then treated with 2% hydrochloric acid at 100° for 1½ hours in order to liberate humic matter combined with calcium, aluminium, iron and other metallic oxides and also to hydrolyse the decomposable carbohydrate (hemicelluloses etc) and the process was repeated thrice when it was supposed to be complete. The soil was then treated with sufficient water at 100° to free it from acid and to remove all the water-soluble products. In order to extract humic matter the soil was then treated with 4% potassium hydroxide solution in the cold and the mixture was kept stirred in a closed vessel for 8-10 hours. The use of ammonia was apparently not advisable for the extraction in view of the investigations of Fuchs and Leopold who showed that ammonia is very strongly adsorbed by humic acid and possibly may also introduce amide groups into the humic acid molecule. The cold alkali extraction was repeated thrice and the clear dark coloured humate solutions were combined, diluted, filtered and the filtrate acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated humic acid was allowed to settle. The clear supernatant liquid was decanted off and the precipitate was shaken up again with fresh water and the process of washing by decantation was continued for 7-8 times within 6-7 days. At the end of this period the acid had a tendency to remain suspended or to pass into a colloidal solution. The acid was then separated by centrifuging. The isolated humic acid was again dissolved in 4% potassium hydroxide solution and precipitated by dilute hydrochloric acid and the washing and centrifuging repeated. The acid was then dried at 80°. The dry acid was next treated with hot alcohol under reflux to separate the alcohol-soluble portion (hymatomelanolic acid). The alcohol-insoluble portion was filtered off and dried at 80°. This alcohol-insoluble humic acid was then treated with sufficient amount of acetyl bromide in a specially made all-glass extraction

apparatus at 80-90° for 7-10 days with frequent shaking. The filtered residue was dried at 80° for some time, then washed with ether until free from acetyl bromide and then again dried at 80-85° to a constant weight.

A scheme of the different ways of fractionating the soil organic matter is given below.

The commercial humic acids obtained from Messrs Merck and Schuchardt were first dissolved in 4% alkali and then precipitated by dilute hydrochloric acid. Alcohol and acetyl bromide extractions were also done in these cases.

The humic acids thus obtained from four sources, Messrs Merck, Schuchardt and from two Assam soils, were analysed for C, H, N, ash, methoxyl, acetyl etc. The results of analysis are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

	Alcohol-insoluble humic acids.			Alcohol-soluble humatomelanolic acids.			
	Merck.	Schn.	Derby soil.	Saph. soil.	Merck.	Schn.	Derby soil.
Ash	3%	8.86%	5.2%	7.2%	1.68%	1.45%	4.5%
N	1.6	1.2	1.22	3.6	1.26	0.87	1.05
OMe	2.11	2.55	3.99	5.4	2.31	4.18	4.6
Acetyl	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Carbon	55.5	55.2	54.0	55.12	58.8	57.8	59.2
H	5.2	4.6	5.0	5.63	5.6	5.1	4.51
Furfural-yielding complexes.	Nil	Nil	Traces	Traces	Nil	Nil	Nil
HCHO-yielding group	Nil	Nil	Traces	Traces	Nil	Nil	Nil

The ash in the different humic acid is not negligible. The ash in the peat humic acids (Merck and Schuchardt) was of greyish white colour and was found to contain iron, silica, aluminium, magnesium and traces of copper. But the ash in the soil humic acids was of a reddish brown colour indicating the presence of a high percentage of iron. The alcohol-soluble portions had lower amount of ash. Methoxyl-content in all the humic acids was not very high, while none of the humic acids contained acetyl groups. Barium salts of all the acids were prepared. Equivalent weights were calculated from the percentage of barium. This will be discussed in a separate paper.

TABLE II.

	Acetyl bromide-insoluble humic acid.			
	Merck.	Schuchardt.	Derby soil.	Saphinjuri soil.
Ash	2.09%	5.16%	2.02%	3.5%
N	1.93	1.4	2.8	3.2
C	56.2	56.8	58.3	56.0
H	5.1	4.85	5.2	5.5
OMe	1.79	2.29	3.26	3.8
Acetyl	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
HCHO-yielding groups	"	"		
Furfural-yielding complexes	"			

The ash content of all the humic acids has been fairly reduced. With the exception of one, the nitrogen-content has been increased. The methoxyl-contents have been lowered though they are not equal in all cases. Some of the previous investigators have found comparatively large amounts of methoxyl in some of the humic acids (*e.g.*, soil and peat); this is due probably to incomplete purification. Though Fuchs and some other investigators have demonstrated the presence of acetyl in soil humic acid, the presence of this group is not noticed in the present work.

With a view to seeing whether the humic acids contain any carbohydrate group (which may have survived the treatment with 2% hydrochloric acid at 100°) one of the substances was distilled with 100 c.c. of 12% hydrochloric acid, but the distillate gave only a slight yellowish colouration with phloroglucinol indicating the absence of any appreciable amount of furfural or furfural-yielding complexes.

In order to see whether the humic acid has any formaldehyde-yielding groups (methylenedioxy-) 0.5 g. of the acid was distilled with 100 c.c. of 28% sulphuric acid. 10 C.c. of the distillate were treated with Schryver's reagent; but no appreciable red colour was developed indicating that humic acids either from peat or soil do not contain any formaldehyde-yielding groups.

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